

Low Light Face Image Enhancement using Modified Histogram Equalization Techniques

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Abstract: Image enhancement methods were usually utilized to upgrade the visual nature of an image for human discernment or to improve explicit highlights for additional examination. These strategies are normally applied in image processing for the reduction of unwanted distribution or noise content decrease. In this work, various modified Histogram Equalization methods were employed to enhance the low-light images. The parameters namely, Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Multi-Scale Structural Similarity Index (MSIM), Structural Similarity Index (SSIM), and Entropy were evaluated on different sizes of images. The experiment was successfully executed with valid results by comparing an enhanced image with an original grey image that helped to generate more definite image information or features.

Keywords: HE, CLAHE, CLAHESV, MGPAHE, BSUHE, FLAHE

I. INTRODUCTION

A concrete mix Image processing, the image enhancement procedures were utilized to improve the visual appearance of an image and also to separate useful information from it. This can include procedures, for example, adjustment of brightness, contrast, and sharpness, removal of unwanted distortions or noise contents, and improvement or enhanced information or more definite features. Image enhancement is helpful in the detection, recognition, and analysis of a specific object. The enhancement of the image can make up for limits in an image obtaining frameworks or ecological circumstances, like low lighting or unfortunate differences. It can help with the representation and examination of various images in different fields, including medication, remote detecting, observation, diversion, and so on. Image enhancement techniques can be applied to either color or grey images.

From the various surveys, it is viewable such that, Grayscale images are easier and require less computational assets for handling contrasted with a variety of images. In certain applications, a variety of data may not be pertinent or accessible, so upgrading grayscale images straightforwardly fills the need. Some image-handling strategies and calculations are innately intended for grayscale images, making them more appropriate for explicit assignments. Image enhancement techniques might act contrastingly relying upon the size and resolution of an image. The large-sized images might require more computational assets and handling time compared with more modest ones. Assessing the presentation and adequacy of image improvement calculations across different sizes helps in grasping their adaptability and generalizability. Various applications might include images of various sizes, so it's fundamental to survey how well improvement methods perform across this scope of sizes to guarantee their materialness in genuine situations.

The motivation behind image enhancement calculation for low-light images is to expand the distinction between the highlights of various articles in the picture, smother the elements that are not fascinating, further develop the image quality, and improve the data. The different enhancement strategies, including their standards and enhancements, are presented from three classes namely, Histogram Equalization (HE), Gray Level Transformation (GLT), and Retinex-based methods, and

machine learning methods were reviewed [1]. HE, Adaptive Histogram Equalization (AHE), and Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) image enhancement methods were experimented on different images in the MATLAB platform. Various procedures have their upsides and downsides so here the juxtaposition of the different strategies has been finished alongside the computation of the different picture boundaries like - Standard Deviation, Mean, Mode, Medians, and Mean Squared Blunder for these improvement methods [2].

Various review plans of image enhancement give an exhaustive outline of various strategies for modern imperfection identification. For this reason, the models were separated into gatherings and introduced exclusively. The aftereffects of the strategies are momentous. The field is still generally youthful, which makes the accomplishments of the research local area much more amazing [3]. The image enhancement techniques namely, CLAHE, adjustment algorithm, and Laplacian filter were utilized and experimented on DRIVE and forty image databases from COVID-19 radiography, endometrioma-11, Normal brain-MRI-6, and simple-breast-cyst-2 in MATLAB platform. Here various parameters namely, Entropy, Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR), Contrast to Noise Ratio (CNR), Mean Square Error (MSE), and Contrast to Noise were evaluated successfully [4]. In Image processing, one of the troublesome issues is image restoration and correction. The objective of an image upgrade is to change a photograph with the goal that the result is more qualified for a specific reason than the first photograph. Computerized picture upgrade strategies offer different choices for improving the tasteful allure of images. The concepts of digital image processing, image correction, restoration, HE, Log transform, local information, Threshold addition, contrast stretch, fuzzy logic derivative techniques, and unsharp masking were reviewed [5].

A new non-uniform and low-light image enhancement method based on weighted guided image filtering was presented. The illumination procedure follows the AHE with the reflection component and then fuses the illumination reflection component and Color restoration. The experiment was successfully executed on CMU-PIE, Yale B, and Digital Camera Data (DICM) databases [6]. The HE, AHE, and CLAHE techniques were utilized successfully to improve the contrast level of the iris image. The parameters namely, Mean Square Error (MSE) and Square root OF Mean Square Error (RSME) were evaluated. The best outcomes utilize the CLAHE strategy. Yet, generally speaking, because of the PSNR values, the three techniques are great strategies for expanding the iris picture contrast since they have a typical PSNR esteem above 30dB [7].

In the primary proposition HE considering the way that the picture gets to was once applied without the utilization of the inborn limit inside MATLAB. Here, all along, a concealing picture concerning a was once picked what's more, the picture was changed between a grayscale image. After this change, histogram evening out used to be applied concerning the grayscale image [8]. The preprocessing methods namely, grey conversion, HE, gamma intensity correction, normalization of contrast, and feature extraction methods namely, Discrete Wavelet Transform, Laplacian of Gaussian, and Logarithmic filtering were utilized in a hybrid manner for face recognition and experimented on their database with a valid result [9] [10] [11]. The various single and hybrid versions of preprocessing and feature extraction methods along with machine learning algorithms were reviewed with various results on different databases [12].

Image Quality Evaluation assumes an exceptionally critical part in computerized picture-handling applications. The measurements of Mean Square Error (MSE), PSNR, SSIM, and Features Similarity Index Matrix (FSIM) are applied in this paper to get the best quality measurement. The experiment was done by reenacting tests utilizing Gaussian clamor through the Gaussian separating method [13]. A modified HE plan to utilize a distinction of histogram canisters has been proposed. The central thought of the proposed technique is to find out the contrast between the quantities of pixels in histogram canisters of an information picture and that of the conventional HE image. The determined contrast of each canister is divided into various blocks in light of reach standards [14]. From the survey, it is observed the image enhancement scheme can be developed by using specific suitable techniques by considering different sizes of an image that helped to generate more suitable features

for further processes in image processing like object detection, recognition, image feature extraction, and so on.

II. METHODOLOGY

The proposed flow of Low Light Face Image Enhancement is shown in Figure 1 and here Various Image Enhancement techniques were employed on resized grey scale face images such that,

Figure 1. Proposed flow of Low Light Face Image Enhancement

A. Histogram Equalization (HE):

Histogram Equalization is a strategy to improve the image contrast by fanning out the pixel/intensity values over the whole powerful reach. The change capability is obtained from the total circulation capability (TCC) of the image's histogram values. The Transformation function of HE is given by

$$HE(r) = \frac{R-1}{PQ} \sum_{j=0}^r n_j \quad (1)$$

Where n_j sum of j levels of cumulative histogram intensity, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, PQ is the total intensity levels, and R is the intensity level number.

B. Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE):

Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization is the modified version of AHE that is utilized to limit the amplification of contrast levels in the neighborhood which helps to prevent the over-amplification of noise of an image. The CLAHE is given by

$$CLAHE(r) = \frac{R-1}{|M(x,y)|} \min(\sum_{z \in M(x,y)} H(Z), k) \quad (2)$$

Where $H(Z)$ represents the neighborhood histograms value, $|M(x,y)|$ represents the neighborhood number of pixels, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, R is the intensity level number, and k is the constant value of the predefined limit such that If the sum of values of the histogram exceeds the k value then, the histogram value is reduced such that the sum equals k .

C. CLAHE with Spatial Variations (CLAHESV):

CLAHE with Spatial Variation is used to improve CLAHE by initialization information spatially into the contrast level enhancement process. Rather than applying CLAHE consistently across the whole image, it isolates the image into areas and applies CLAHE autonomously to every locale, taking into account both force conveyance and spatial connections among adjoining districts. The CLAHESV is given by,

$$CLAHESV(r) = \frac{R-1}{|M_i(x,y)|} \min(\sum_{z \in M_i(x,y)} H(Z), k_i) \quad (3)$$

Where $H(Z)$ represents the neighborhood histogram value of the region $|M_i(x,y)|$, $|M_i(x,y)|$ represents the number of pixels in the region $|M(x,y)|$, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, R is the intensity level number, and k_i the constant value predefined limit to a specific region of $|M_i(x,y)|$ that can be altered based on the region's local characteristic level such that it can identified based histogram level of each region that helped for automatic control of contrast levels.

D. Brightness Saving Unique Histogram Equalization (BSUHE):

Brightness Saving Unique Histogram Equalization is an augmentation of conventional HE strategies that means upgrading the contrast level of an image while safeguarding the general splendor. It accomplishes this by adjusting the histogram evening-out interaction to think about both the difference upgrade and the safeguarding of the image's mean brilliance. The BSUHE is given by

$$BSUHE(r) = \frac{R-1}{PQ} \sum_{j=0}^r n_j + b \quad (4)$$

Where n_j sum of j levels of cumulative histogram intensity, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, PQ is the total intensity levels, R is the intensity level number, b is the brightness saving scheme that gives guarantees the brightness mean of the upgraded or enhanced image stays near the mean

splendor of the first. The b can be determined by adjusting HE based on the mean value of brightness or consolidating a punishment term in the enhancement cycle to limit changes in brightness.

E. Fuzzy logic-based Adaptive Histogram Equalization (FLAHE):

Fuzzy logic-based Adaptive Histogram Equalization consolidates the flexibility of AHE with fluffy rationale strategies to improve contrast in the image in light of neighborhood attributes while thinking about vulnerability and unclearness. Fuzzy logic takes into consideration the portrayal of uncertain data, making it appropriate for changing the upgrade cycle because of differing nearby picture qualities. The FLAHE represented that depends on the choice of the fuzzy set of rules, fuzzy membership functions, and the implementation details. Generally, FLAHE is given by

$$FLAHE(r) = \frac{R-1}{PQ} \sum_{j=0}^r n_j \mu_j \tag{5}$$

Where n_j sum of j levels of cumulative histogram intensity, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, PQ is the total intensity levels, R is the intensity level number, b is the brightness saving scheme that gives guarantees the brightness mean of the upgraded or enhanced image stays near the mean splendor of the first, μ_j the fuzzy logic membership value of the level of intensity based on contrast and brightness level and j determined by the inference system of the fuzzy.

F. Multiscale Gaussian Pyramid Adaptive Histogram Equalization: (MGPAHE):

AHE with multiscale examination utilizing a Gaussian pyramid deterioration includes decaying the information image into different scales utilizing a Gaussian pyramid, applying AHE freely to each scale, and afterward remaking the last upgraded picture by joining the improved scales. The MGPAHE is given by

$$HE(r) = \frac{R-1}{PQ} \sum_{j=0}^r n_{ij} \tag{6}$$

Where n_{ij} is the number of the intensity value of j in the I scale, r is the intensity level from 0 to $R-1$, PQ is the total intensity level at the scale i , and R is the intensity level number.

III.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experiment was evaluated on 5 low light-face images which were captured using 5 Megha-Pixel cameras and face images were detected by Viola Jones Algorithm. They were initially converted into greyscale images and then resized into 125 x 125, 256 x 256, 512 x 512, and 1024 x 1014 resized grayscale face images. The HE, CLAHE, CLAHEHSV, MGPAHE, BSUAHE, and FLAHE enhancement methods were employed on each resized grayscale face image. The output of various image enhancement techniques is shown in Table 1 below.

Image	Original Image	Gray Scale Image	HE	CLAHE	CLAHEHSV	FLAHE	BSUAHE	MGPAHE
Image 1								
Image 2								
Image 3								
Image 4								
Image 5								

Table 1. Output of Various Image Enhancement Techniques

The evaluation parameter considered for the experiment is as follows

A. Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR): PSNR computes the nature of a remade signal contrasted with the first sign. In image processing, PSNR is regularly utilized to evaluate the distinction between the first and the upgraded / Enhanced image. For better quality, the PSNR value should be higher and it is measured in db.

B. Mean Absolute Error (MAE): MAE estimates the typical outright contrast between the pixel upsides of the first and the improved image. Lower MAE values demonstrate better quality.

C. Mean Structural Similarity Index (MSIM): MSIM is a measurement used to gauge the similitude in primary data between the first and the improved or enhanced image. It is frequently obtained from SSIM which incorporates correlations of luminance, difference, and construction.

D. Structural Similarity Index (SSIM): SSIM is a measurement used to gauge the comparability between two pictures. It considers luminance, contrast, and underlying closeness. Higher SSIM values demonstrate higher comparability between the first and improved or enhanced images.

E. Entropy: Entropy estimates the arbitrariness or vulnerability in the pixel forces of an image. Lower entropy values show not so much haphazardness but rather more consistency in the pixel values.

Table 2. Evaluation of PSNR, MAE, MSIM, SSIM, ENTROPY parameters

Image	Image size	SNR					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
Image 1	128 x 128	8.8454	12.652	13.621	8.318	12.72	23.158
	256 x 256	8.8488	12.554	13.543	8.272	12.723	23.171
	512 x 512	8.8487	12.535	13.541	8.212	12.723	23.173
	1024 x 1024	8.8488	12.582	13.58	8.211	12.723	23.168
	Image size	MAE					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	8482.8	3530.7	2824.5	4078.91	3475.9	328.11
	256 x 256	8476.2	3611.3	2875.9	4008.11	3474	355.55
	512 x 512	8476.3	3627.5	2877.4	4089.45	3473.9	366.55
	1024 x 1024	8476.2	3588	2851.6	4091.28	3473.7	384.21
	Image size	MSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.61178	0.64552	0.7714	0.5789	0.93532	0.96733
	256 x 256	0.63386	0.60803	0.73476	0.5784	0.9238	0.96602
	512 x 512	0.67665	0.61754	0.73961	0.5764	0.91735	0.96721
	1024 x 1024	0.73745	0.67619	0.7847	0.5661	0.92144	0.97052
	Image size	SSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.47702	0.48516	0.57344	0.43736	0.89545	0.91223
	256 x 256	0.51763	0.53723	0.60436	0.45722	0.90703	0.92333
512 x 512	0.56528	0.60597	0.65262	0.46869	0.92476	0.93211	
1024 x 1024	0.61229	0.68324	0.70339	0.45003	0.94193	0.95631	
Image size	Entropy						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	5.7821	7.6032	7.1769	6.4215	6.4149	7.2712	
256 x 256	5.7856	7.6487	7.2454	6.4329	6.4188	7.2118	
512 x 512	5.7853	7.6572	7.2541	6.436	6.4281	7.2811	
1024 x 1024	5.7858	7.6545	7.25	6.4364	6.4287	7.3153	
Image	Image size	PSNR					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
Image 2	128 x 128	8.8474	12.551	13.581	8.308	12.712	23.137
	256 x 256	8.8487	12.553	13.533	8.264	12.718	23.172
	512 x 512	8.8485	12.530	13.562	8.208	12.726	23.172
	1024 x 1024	8.8489	12.592	13.59 9	8.219	12.727	23.156
	Image size	MAE					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHEsv	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	8482.21	3530.78	2825.51	4077.98	3474.7 7	329.22
	256 x 256	8477.21	3611.12	2877.92	4008.12	3474.22	353.55
	512 x 512	8478.42	3628.55	2878.41	4087.23	3473.75	367.58
	1024 x 1024	8480.21	3587.12	2854.61	4088.43	3473.81	388.26

Image size	MSIM						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	0.61155	0.64548	0.7801	0.5799	0.93632	0.96723	
256 x 256	0.63389	0.60812	0.7347	0.5774	0.92238	0.96612	
512 x 512	0.67669	0.61756	0.73863	0.5774	0.91855	0.96621	
1024 x 1024	0.73749	0.67628	0.78571	0.5671	0.92124	0.97033	
Image size	SSIM						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	0.47711	0.48521	0.57348	0.43766	0.89556	0.91123	
256 x 256	0.51762	0.53724	0.60437	0.45752	0.90733	0.92323	
512 x 512	0.56577	0.60588	0.65252	0.46879	0.92466	0.93261	
1024 x 1024	0.61218	0.68354	0.70438	0.45013	0.94233	0.95681	
Image size	Entropy						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	5.7811	7.6102	7.1779	6.4323	6.415	7.2731	
256 x 256	5.7856	7.6477	7.2454	6.4328	6.4182	7.2618	
512 x 512	5.7854	7.6582	7.2548	6.4262	6.4287	7.2619	
1024 x 1024	5.7888	7.6595	7.2588	6.4374	6.4287	7.3263	
Image	Image size	PSNR					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
Image 3	128 x 128	8.8452	12.654	13.622	8.358	12.723	23.138
	256 x 256	8.8479	12.554	13.541	8.252	12.724	23.171
	512 x 512	8.8485	12.537	13.541	8.232	12.724	23.174
	1024 x 1024	8.8489	12.572	13.581	8.212	12.724	23.165
	Image size	MAE					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	8482.8	3532.7	2834.5	4078.82	3474.9	338.12
	256 x 256	8476.2	3617.3	2865.9	4018.13	3474.66	355.57
	512 x 512	8476.5	3626.5	2877.21	4079.40	3473.92	368.58
	1024 x 1024	8476.7	3588.3	2879.6	4091.22	3473.78	383.131
	Image size	MSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.61168	0.64552	0.77145	0.5787	0.93502	0.96721
	256 x 256	0.63375	0.60821	0.73477	0.5785	0.92362	0.96612
	512 x 512	0.67664	0.61753	0.73981	0.5765	0.91765	0.96732
	1024 x 1024	0.73747	0.67618	0.78462	0.5664	0.92184	0.97153
Image size	SSIM						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	0.47692	0.48508	0.57342	0.43746	0.89547	0.91224	
256 x 256	0.51773	0.53711	0.60477	0.45722	0.90719	0.92332	
512 x 512	0.56568	0.60588	0.65252	0.46879	0.92478	0.93215	
1024 x 1024	0.61779	0.68359	0.70389	0.45884	0.94083	0.95656	
Image size	Entropy						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	5.7828	7.6036	7.1767	6.4218	6.4160	7.2721	
256 x 256	5.7847	7.6479	7.2450	6.4335	6.4168	7.2719	
512 x 512	5.7848	7.6578	7.2552	6.4368	6.4272	7.2729	
1024 x 1024	5.7852	7.6589	7.251	6.4379	6.4277	7.3163	
Image	Image size	PSNR					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
Image 4	128 x 128	8.8457	12.655	13.632	8.368	12.723	23.158
	256 x 256	8.8477	12.555	13.542	8.222	12.724	23.170
	512 x 512	8.8489	12.548	13.543	8.237	12.725	23.171
	1024 x 1024	8.8489	12.576	13.584	8.232	12.725	23.173
	Image size	MAE					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	8482.6	3528.7	2833.3	4078.87	3474.92	338.22
	256 x 256	8476.12	3629.2	2864.9	4018.23	3474.76	355.37
	512 x 512	8476.4	3626.5	2877.21	4079.41	3473.92	368.59
	1024 x 1024	8477.6	3588.2	2878.7	4091.23	3473.88	383.14
	Image size	MSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.61169	0.64555	0.77144	0.5785	0.93512	0.96728
	256 x 256	0.63365	0.60827	0.73458	0.5785	0.92364	0.96617

	512 x 512	0.67677	0.61755	0.73977	0.5767	0.91764	0.96742
	1024 x 1024	0.73787	0.67622	0.78461	0.5665	0.92186	0.97143
	Image size	SSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.47672	0.48517	0.57422	0.43646	0.89587	0.91234
	256 x 256	0.51783	0.53701	0.60470	0.45628	0.90739	0.92532
	512 x 512	0.56589	0.60388	0.65258	0.46773	0.92478	0.93616
	1024 x 1024	0.61889	0.68259	0.70277	0.45938	0.94089	0.95557
	Image size	Entropy					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	5.7827	7.6132	7.1768	6.4228	6.4164	7.2721
	256 x 256	5.7848	7.6477	7.2466	6.4285	6.4177	7.2728
	512 x 512	5.7848	7.6577	7.2572	6.4388	6.4278	7.2727
	1024 x 1024	5.7853	7.6585	7.2533	6.4399	6.4278	7.3166
Image	Image size	PSNR					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
Image 5	128 x 128	8.8439	12.658	13.592	8.368	12.722	23.147
	256 x 256	8.8448	12.661	13.581	8.263	12.722	23.176
	512 x 512	8.8488	12.602	13.582	8.239	12.725	23.178
	1024 x 1024	8.8491	12.611	13.601	8.217	12.726	23.169
	Image size	MAE					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	8479.6	3533.2	2836.4	4078.78	3474.89	338.09
	256 x 256	8476.11	3637.8	2864.7	4018.13	3474.68	355.77
	512 x 512	8477.49	3628.8	2872.21	4079.44	3473.88	369.98
	1024 x 1024	8477.8	3590.8	2878.3	4091.28	3473.89	387.19
	Image size	MSIM					
		HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE
	128 x 128	0.61165	0.64558	0.77155	0.5789	0.93511	0.96761
	256 x 256	0.63366	0.60820	0.73467	0.5788	0.92462	0.9666
512 x 512	0.67666	0.61763	0.73983	0.5770	0.91745	0.96734	
1024 x 1024	0.73750	0.67628	0.78563	0.5674	0.92194	0.97223	
Image size	SSIM						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	0.47790	0.48558	0.57453	0.43756	0.89544	0.91230	
256 x 256	0.51781	0.53776	0.61487	0.45733	0.90719	0.92341	
512 x 512	0.56588	0.60598	0.65272	0.46970	0.92479	0.93209	
1024 x 1024	0.61756	0.68389	0.71380	0.46880	0.94381	0.95702	
Image size	Entropy						
	HE	CLAHE	CLAHESV	MGPAHE	BSUAHE	FLAHE	
128 x 128	5.7829	7.6031	7.1768	6.4218	6.4121	7.2723	
256 x 256	5.7847	7.6477	7.2462	6.4330	6.4101	7.2718	
512 x 512	5.7847	7.6578	7.2533	6.4383	6.4233	7.2739	
1024 x 1024	5.7853	7.6588	7.2514	6.4380	6.4287	7.3193	

III. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In general, for applications in image processing like detection, recognition, feature extraction, and analysis it is necessary to enhance the image before the next procedure. In this work, HE, CLAHE, CLAHESV, MGPAHE, BSUAHE, and FLAHE enhancement methods were utilized successfully. The experiment was successfully evaluated on 5 low light images which were captured randomly and the face image was detected using the Viola-Jones Algorithm. The PSNR, MAE, MSIM, SSIM, and entropy parameters were calculated on 125 x 125, 256 x 256, 512 x 512, and 1024 x 1014 resized grayscale face images. From the results, it can be observed that BSUAHE and FLAHE methods give more valuable results compared to HE, CLAHE, CLAHESV, and MGPAHE methods. It concludes that lower-sized images are more suitable when analyzing the larger level of application with less definite image features and also it gives a different set of results depending on the type of camera where images were captured. In future work, it is necessary to make use of different camera types of large set face images and employ various image enhancement methods to extract more definite image features for face detection, recognition, and analysis

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